

Cu removal to ppb levels via iron coagulation and biosolid conditioning

T. Y. Yeh^{1*}, Fred Cannon²⁻¹ *Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, National University of Kaohsiung, Taiwan* ² *the Pennsylvania State University*

Correspondence to:

Prof. T. Y. Yeh

National University of Kaohsiung

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering

Kaohsiung 811, Taiwan

Abstract

Cu removal to ppb levels was achieved in an activated sludge system by employing ion bio-flocculation and sludge storage conditions. Cu removal correlated to an increase in extra-cellular polymer polysaccharide that was produced by microorganisms within achieved sludge. Cu levels between 15 a 35 ppb were achieved when employing coagulant dosage of 15 meg/L (as Fe) and when allowing 18 to 26 hours of sludge storage conditionings enhance the precondition of extracellular polymer polysaccharides. Maximum Cu removal occurred in a pH range 6.5 to 8.8. Sequential chemical extraction test were conducted to appraise the extent which cu associated with the various components within biosold.

Key Words: Cu, extracellar polysaccharide, iron coagulant

• Introduction

Bacterial extracellular polymers are comprised primarily of polysaccharides and proteins. Polysaccharides have been monitored with the Ruthenium /rd (Figueroa and silverstein, 1989) and India ink.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Plant, biostimulators, and soil preparation

Vetiver and sunflower were collected from the University of Kaohsiung campus wetlands (22°73'N, 120°28'E) precultured for 5 days and carefully washed with distilled water. Plant samples were dried at 103°C in an oven until completely dried.

2.2 Total metal content, soil retained fractionation and plant metal uptake analysis

2.3. Harvested Plant tissue and final soil metal content analysis

Plant after last session of operation was harvested, carefully washed, and air dried for metal analysis. Plant samples were dried at 103°C in an oven until completely dried. Dried plant samples were divided into root and shoot for metal accumulation assessment. These pretreated plants were digested in a solution containing 11:1 HNO₃:HCl solution via a microwave digestion apparatus (Mars 230/60, CEM Corporation) and diluted to 100 mL with deionized water. 0.2 g of dried soil adding *aqua regia* reagent for microwave digestion and 2.5 g of dried soil for sequential extraction experiments. Metals analyses were conducted via an atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS, Perkin Elmer).

The fractionation of soil retained metal was investigated by a sequential extraction technique where soil samples were placed in a plastic bottle then shaking for proper mixing overnight and subjected to a five-step

serial extraction procedure. The procedure of sequential chemical extraction used in this study includes a series of reagents which represented as exchangeable (1 M KNO₃), inorganically bound (0.5 M KF), organically bound (0.1 M Na₄P₂O₇), Fe and Mn-oxide bound (0.3 M Na₃C₆H₅O₇, 1 M NaHCO₃ and 0.5 g Na₂S₂O₄), and sulfide (6 M HNO₃) forms, respectively (Tessier et al. 1979).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)-energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy

Pretreated macrophyte samples were gold-coated for SEM observation with qualitative EDX analysis. Specifically, grinded and dried samples were mounted on carbon tape and sputter coated in gold. A Hitachi S-4300 SEM (Tokyo, Japan) was used to capture micrographs. The elements C, O, Cu, and Zn were detected using a SEM coupled with an EDX spectroscopy at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV.

2.4 Data and Statistical analysis

Data were evaluated relative to the control to understand their statistical variation. Metal concentration of plants was recorded as mg of metal per kilogram of dry biomass. A triplicate of soil and plant samples from each treatment were recorded and used for statistical analyses. Statistical significance was assessed using mean comparison test. Differences between treatment concentration means of parameters were determined by Student's t test. A level of $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant was used in all comparisons. Means are reported mean \pm standard deviation. All statistical analyses were performed with Microsoft Office EXCEL 2003.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 COPPER REMOVAL BY CONDITIONED BIOSOLIDS AND PRE-PRECIPITATED IRON COAGULANTS.

The aforementioned tests all employed iron coagulants that were precipitating at the same time as the copper was becoming incorporated into the particulates, i.e. possibly via a coprecipitation mechanism with iron coagulants. The purpose of the next tests was to investigate whether pre-formed iron flocs could perform as well at reducing copper levels in the supernatant. The experiment was carried out by employing pre-precipitated iron coagulants and conditioned biosolids that were treated under condition *a) closed-to-oxygen without mixing*, *(c) low oxygen with slow mixing*, and *(d) aerobic with complete mixing* for 24 hours. 300 ppb of copper was spiked into the solution prior to iron dosing. 0.1 M of iron stock solution was preadjusted pH by using NaOH to form iron flocs. Then 15 mg/L (as Fe) of this pre-precipitated iron solution was added into sludge samples. After rapid mixing, slow mixing, and settling, the supernatant was taken to analyze total and dissolved (0.45 μm) copper levels. The results are shown on Fig. 4.17.

Under condition *a) closed-to-oxygen without mixing*, *(c) low oxygen with slow mixing*, and *(d) aerobic with complete mixing*, the total copper concentrations were 34, 34, and 44 ppb, respectively, whereas the dissolved copper levels were 18, 22, and 32 ppb, respectively. Thus, the dissolved copper (i.e. <0.45 μm) represented 53% of total copper under condition *(a) (closed-to-oxygen without mixing)*, 64% under condition *(c) (low oxygen with slow mixing)*, and 77% under condition *(d) (aerobic with complete mixing)*, respectively.

When comparing these results to those in Figure 4.15, it is noted that copper removal rate via pre-precipitated iron flocs was slightly lower than that by coprecipitation of iron chloride under condition *a) closed-to-oxygen without mixing* and *(c) low oxygen with slow mixing*. Copper removal via pre-precipitated iron flocs did not perform as well as via coprecipitation by ferric chloride within sludges that were storage conditioned under low oxygen and oxygen limited conditions.

Specifically, for condition *a) (closed to oxygen without mixing)*, when the iron was co-precipitated, total copper amounted to 26 ppb, whereas when iron was pre-precipitated, total copper amounted to 34 ppb, which was considerably higher. Likewise, for condition *c) (low oxygen with slow mixing)*, these values were 31 ppb for the co-precipitated, as compared to 34 ppb for the pre-precipitated tests. There is even greater disparity when comparing the copper fraction that passed an 0.45 filter. Under the condition *d) aerobic with completely mixing*,

copper removal by either co-precipitation or pre-precipitation of iron coagulants was comparable.

The practical application of these results to full-scale systems is that iron flocs that have been recycled through the aeration tank, clarifier, and selector through several cycles will not remove copper as effectively as will iron that has been freshly dosed into the process.

3.1 SEQUENTIAL CHEMICAL FRACTIONATION

Sequential chemical fractionation was adapted from the study of Yeoman et al. (1993) and Oake et al. (1984). They proposed that the sludge components that copper associated with could be generally characterized by selective chemical extraction techniques.

On the basis of their work, we incorporated herein a sequential extraction procedure that sequentially employed KNO_3 , KF, $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$, EDTA, 6 M HNO_3 , and concentrated (69.5 %) HNO_3 . These extractions were proposed by Oake et al. (1984) and Yeoman et al. (1993), to respectively represent the exchangeable, adsorbed, organically bound, carbonate, sulfide (etc.), and residual forms of copper. The residual form was considered the most stable form because it required the most drastic extraction reagent (concentrated nitric acid) and treatment (digestion) for its removal. These extraction procedures might not represent truly distinct divisions between different copper forms since reagents might not be completely selective for one particular form as discussed in the literature review above, none-the-less, they were perceived by Oake et al. (1984) and Yeoman et al. (1993) to provide functionally useful insight.

Sequential extractions were conducted on sludge that had experienced 24 hours of storage under conditions *a) closed-to-oxygen without mixing*, *(c) low oxygen with slow mixing*, and *(d) aerobic with complete mixing*. The storage-conditioning sludges then received sequential chemical fractionation. The results of the sequential extraction and shown in Fig. 4.18, and the average percentage values highlighted by the numerical value listed at the top of each bar. The statistical analysis results results are also shown on Table 4.1.

Overall, more total copper was retained by condition *a) biosolids* (955 mg/kg) and condition *c) biosolids* (943 mg/kg) than was retained by the *d) aerated biosolids* (902 mg/kg). Moreover, the overall trends were similar: for all three storage conditions, a higher fraction of the copper was extracted via $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ (21-26 %), EDTA (26-30 %), and 6 M HNO_3 (18-23%) than was extracted via KNO_3 (3-10 %), KF (13-17 %), or concentrated HNO_3 (5-7%). However, there were statistically significant distinctions among there, which are discussed as follows:

More copper was extracted by KNO_3 which represented the exchangeable forms under the d) aerobic with complete mixing condition, whereas the a) closed-to-oxygen treatment yielded the least exchangeable (KNO_3) extract. F-test results illustrated that copper extracted from three conditioned sludges was statistically different. One might anticipated that the exchangeable copper would originated soluble copper ions that had become exchangeably bound within solids. In correlation previous result (Figure 4.16), the well-aerated samples contained higher proportions of soluble copper. The exchangeable forms of copper are more mobile and can easily leach out after sludge subjected to final land disposal. This finding demonstrated another advantage of conditioning sludge under oxygen limited conditions.

The copper forms extracted by $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$, which was equivalent to organic bound form, were the highest under the a) closed-to-oxygen without mixing condition. F-test also demonstrated that the average copper levels were statistically different among these three storage conditioning conditions. These results illustrated that more copper was bound with organic matter under non-oxygenated condition. Previously, more exopolymer polysaccharides were found under the same storage condition. These findings might be correlated with one another.

Copper extracted by HNO_3 , which represents sulfide and possibly other fractions, indicated that more copper bound with sulfide and related forms under non-oxygenated conditions. F-test results also showed that there are statistically differences under three storage conditioning conditions. As preciously indicated, sludge extracted by HNO_3 might not only represent sulfide fraction. These extraction results only partially indicated that more copper was likely precipitated as sulfide fractions. In correlation, sulfide would predominate more in anaerobic, rather than aerobic conditions.

Once again, these extraction procedures may not represent distinct divisions between different copper forms since reagents may not be completely selective for one particular form. The use of chemical reagents to extract a specific form of copper is not precise. It is more appropriate to address that these extractants extract a chemically similar form with some overlap of other forms. Nevertheless, these findings still provide some valuable information regarding to the copper fractions in conditioned sludges.

3.3 PILOT-SCALE EXPERIMENTS

Prior to these fill-and-draw tests, pilot-scale experiments were conducted which did not include the low-air sludge storage conditioning step. These were only marginally successful in achieving reduced copper

levels. Indeed, the limitations of the success served as the motivation to pursue further improvements to the bioferric flocculation method that are described above. Spiking 100 to 300 ppb of cupric chloride into influent, the effluent copper concentration of the control unit (without dosing coagulants) was varied from 50 to 100 ppb. This amounted to a 25 to 50 % of copper removal was attributed to the bacterial enmeshment of the copper. The variation of effluent copper concentration was corresponded with the spiked copper levels. The water quality of trickling filter effluent has also slightly impact on the effluent copper levels. The ionic form experiments employed both alum and iron coagulants addition at two different concentrations of 3 and 5 mg/L (as Fe (III) and Al (III)). These ionic coagulant conditions achieved effluent copper levels of 50 to 75 ppb, which were no better than if no coagulants had been used (Fig 4.19). These results may attributed to the unfavorable conditions for these ionic coagulant to form settleable chemical flocs. The competition of cations and/or protons with copper ions to adsorb onto the surface of biosolids or exopolymer materials might cause these discourage results. Lack of extracellular polymers to bridge the bioflocs and chemical flocs might worsen the settleability of this bioferric flocs, therefore, a decrease of copper removal can be induced.

The experiments employed the prehydrolyzed form of the coagulants, in which FeCl_3 or $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ was mixed in a bottle under conditions that caused the iron or aluminum to form a solid flocculant. This flocculation was accomplished before this solution was added to the pilot columns. Each floc particle was about the size of a sand grain. Jar tests identified that the pH 8 to 10 range achieved the most favorable conditions for creating the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ or $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ flocs before they were introduced into the activated sludge basins. With coagulant dosages of 10 mg/L as Fe or 5 mg/L as Al, or 10 mg/L as Al, the copper concentration of the effluent dropped to around 40 ppb. This contrasted to an effluent copper concentration of the control unit of around 50 to 60 ppb. This result indicated that an additional 20 to 30 % of copper removal could be induced by the contribution of coagulant dosage (Fig 4.20).

These pilot scale experiments demonstrated that prehydrolyzed forms of coagulants performed slightly better copper removal than ionic forms of coagulants without sludge storage conditioning. Even though the alkalinity of tricking filter effluent was sufficient to prevent a pH upset in in aeration columns, the slight decrease of pH may also cause in the inferior copper removal by adding ionic forms of coagulants.

The pilot scale experiments further conducted to study the effect of sludge storage conditioning. Sludge samples were taken from the reactor of control, iron

dosed only, and two iron dosed and sludge storage conditioning. In order to determine the effect of copper removal in these sludge samples, elevated 1,000 ppb of copper was spiked into each sludge in bench scale experiments. After rapid mixing, slow mixing, and settling, the supernatant was analyzed for total copper levels. The results are shown in Fig. 4.21. The remaining total copper concentrations were 95, 52, 20 and 13 ppb for reactors of control, iron dosed, and two iron dosed along with sludge storage conditioning, respectively. These results indicated that sludges experienced storage treatment performed better than sludge either in a control reactor or in a reactor with iron dosed only.

3.6 Phytoattenuation evaluation PCR analysis

Technologies include: gene probes, microarrays, and conventional and real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR), whole genome amplification, sequencing, comparative genomics, and metagenomics. Together these proved unprecedented ability to interrogate the microbial world.

Detection of a specific gene target has become routine practice in most molecular biology laboratories. The ability to analyze 16S rRNA gene sequence using PCR has resulted in a virtual explosion of environmental samples with prior DNA extraction from environmental samples. PCR has revolutionized the ability of researchers to detect specific nucleic acid sequences in isolated as well as in environmental samples. PCR is extremely sensitive able in some cases to detect a single target molecule. PCR assay has been optimized, it is relatively fast and easy to get results in only a few hours, compared to the several days or weeks that may be necessary for cultural methods. FTIR results is shown on Fig. 1. Most are carboxyl, hydroxyl functional groups.

4. Conclusion

Cu removal to ppb levels was achieved in an activated sludge system by employing ion bio-flocculation and sludge storage conditions. Cu removal correlated to an increase in extra-cellular polymer polysaccharide that was produced by microorganisms within activated sludge. Cu levels between 15 to 35 ppb were achieved when employing coagulant dosage of 15 mg/L (as Fe) and when allowing 18 to 26 hours of sludge storage conditionings enhance the precondition of extracellular polymer polysaccharides. Maximum Cu

removal occurred in a pH range 6.5 to 8.8. Sequential chemical extraction tests were conducted to appraise the extent which Cu associated with the various components within biosolid. This technology can be employed for activated sludge system elsewhere without expand the plant capacity and operation cost.

Reference

- C. L. Lin, T. Y. Yeh, "Heavy metals distribution characteristics in different particle size of bottom ash after agglomeration/defluidization at various fluidization parameters", *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 2010, 34, pp 428-437 (SCI)
- Kao, C.M., Wang, J.Y., Chen, K.F., Lee, H.Y., and Wu, M.J. Non-point source pesticide removal by a mountainous wetland, *Wat. Sci. & Tech.*, 46, 199-206, 2002
- Lin CE, Kao CM, Lai YC. Application of integrated GIS and multimedia modeling on NPS pollution evaluation. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 158, 319-331, 2009
- S.W. Chen, C.M. Kao, H.Y. Chien, Y.T. Fu, Y.I. Chang. Use of a Constructed Wetland for Post-treatment of Swine Wastewater, *Environmental Engineering Science*, p 407-417, 2008
- T. Y. Yeh, T. Y. Ke, Y. L. Lin "Algal Growth Control within Natural Water Purification Systems: Macrophyte Light Shading Effects", *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution*, 214, pp 575-586, 2011
- T. Y. Yeh, C. T. Pan, T. Y. Ke, T. W. Kuo, "Organic Matter and Nitrogen Removal within Field-Scale Constructed Wetlands: Reduction Performance and Microbial Identification Studies", *Water Environment Research*, 2010, 82, pp 27-33
- T.Y. Yeh, C.H. Wu, "Pollutants Removal within Hybrid Constructed Wetland Systems in Tropical Regions", *Water Science and Technology*, 2009, 59, pp 233-240
- T. Y. Yeh, C. C. Chou, C. T. Pan "Heavy metal removal within pilot-scale constructed wetlands receiving river water contaminated by confined swine operations", *Desalination*, 2009, 249, pp 368-373
- T.Y. Chen, Kao, C.M., T.Y. Yeh. A.C. Chao. Application of a Constructed Wetland for Industrial Wastewater Treatment, *Chemosphere*, 2006, p 497-502

Figure Captions

- Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of activated sludge
Fig. 2 FTIR result

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of activated sludge

Fig. 2 FTIR result

